

THE EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN THE ORGANIZATION OF PROSECUTORIAL SUPERVISION OVER THE EXECUTION OF LEGISLATION ON JUVENILES

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of the prosecution authorities of developed foreign countries in the life of the country based on their duties. In addition, the best practices of the prosecutor's offices of some foreign countries in protecting the rights of juveniles, organizing prosecutorial supervision over the execution of legislation in this area were analyzed, and proposals and recommendations were developed for introducing their successful aspects into the legislation of our country.

Key words: juveniles, prosecutorial supervision, foreign experience, juvenile justice, criminal prosecution, legal system.

In connection with the improvement of the system for protecting the rights and legitimate interests of juveniles at the international and national levels, paying special attention to ensuring the implementation of legal acts in this area is one of the important tasks facing the prosecution authorities and other agencies. In this regard, it seems important to study the best practices of developed foreign countries in ensuring the legal protection of juveniles by the prosecutor's office, organizing supervision over the execution of legislation in this area, and applying their successful aspects in national legislation and practice of prosecutorial supervision.

In our opinion, it is advisable to take into account the legal structure, the economic potential of the state, the established traditions and conditions in society, and a number of other important aspects when introducing the best practices of developed foreign countries into the organization of prosecutorial activities,

especially prosecutorial supervision over the execution of legislation on juveniles in our country.

The experience of developed foreign countries shows that there is no single approach to protecting the rights and legitimate interests of juveniles and ensuring the rule of law in this area. In addition, given the uniqueness of the tasks of the prosecutor's office in different countries, prosecutorial supervision in the field of juveniles, ensuring the rule of law in the field is also carried out by different state bodies in different countries. In particular, if we turn to the experience of Western countries, then in most of them the prosecution authorities perform such tasks as protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens and combating crime in the courts.

In particular, the main task of the German prosecutor's office is to carry out criminal prosecution [1]. The prosecutor's office in the United States is considered an attorney service and has no analogue in the legal system of other countries, and scientists include it in the executive branch based on the theory of separation of powers [2].

It should be noted that the absence of general control function in the prosecutor's offices of some foreign countries does not mean that there is no prosecutor control (general control) in these countries. In particular, the main tasks performed by prosecutors at all levels in France are the supervision of criminal investigations and trials. The main task of the General Prosecutor is to exercise supervision over the application of criminal law throughout the territory under the jurisdiction of the courts of appeal. The Romanian prosecutor's office protects the general interests of society in court and controls the rule of law. The task of the Polish prosecutor's office is to protect the rule of law and supervise the preliminary investigation [3].

The analysis shows that the system for protecting the rights and legitimate interests of juveniles in the United States, Europe and other developed countries is more developed, and it is advisable to study the best practices of such countries. In particular, the rights and legitimate interests of juveniles in Western Europe and the

United States are protected by juvenile justice, a special legal branch of the state. In addition, if you look at the French experience, then in France the prosecutor's office operates at the courts and is headed by the Minister of Justice [4].

In particular, the prosecutor's office has broad powers to protect the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens in the criminal, civil and administrative spheres. The role of the prosecutor in civil proceedings is determined by the importance of his functions, which is primarily expressed in control over the legality of decisions taken by the courts, protection of the rights of persons with disabilities and juveniles. It should be noted that according to French law, it is mandatory for the public prosecutor to participate in cases such as adoption, determining and changing guardianship and guardianship of juveniles [5].

Also, in the countries of the Middle East, the tasks performed by the prosecutor's office are different, and the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of minors, as well as ensuring the rule of law in this area, is of particular importance for them.

In particular, the prosecutor's office in Japan is organizationally part of the Ministry of Justice and operates based on the principle of a single system. Therefore, compared to other Asia-Pacific countries, their supervisory powers are quite limited, with only the police investigating crimes and overseeing the execution of sentences imposed by courts [6]. It should be noted that special attention is paid to the protection of the rights of juveniles and their social protection by the state in Japan. According to A.N. Larin and I.N. Konoplevoy, "In Japan, the priority form of placement of children left without parental care is placement in orphanages, and family forms of placement are rarely used, which is undoubtedly an expression of trust in state care" [7].

Also, in Azerbaijan, which is currently developing in all aspects of the socio-economic sphere, it is clear that the system for organizing the activities of the prosecutor's office and protecting the rights of minors has its own characteristics.

The Prosecutor's Office of Azerbaijan does not participate in the general and other control procedures over the implementation of the legislation on juveniles [8].

One of the main tasks of the prosecutor's office is to organize of prosecutorial supervision over the execution of legislation on juveniles in the Russian Federation.

For example, in a number of constituent entities of the Federation (in the prosecutor's offices of the Tula, Saratov, Voronezh and other regions), departments for working with juveniles and youth operate in the prosecutor's offices [9].

It is known that juveniles are a category that needs additional guarantees compared to others. However, among juveniles there are also orphans and children deprived of parental care, who need special attention and social protection. In particular, in the Russian Federation, the state ensures the priority of family education and assumes the duties of parents in relation to neglected children. In particular, hotlines have been set up in the regional prosecutor's offices on the protection of the rights of minors in institutions for orphans and children left without parental care.

It should be recognized that Kazakhstan is one of the countries with advanced experience in protecting the rights of juveniles and organizing the prosecutor's control over the implementation of laws in this area. In particular, Kazakhstan has ratified about 60 international documents on human rights, more than 15 of which are directly related to children's rights.

Another noteworthy point is that in the Republic of Kazakhstan, the system of "juvenile justice" has been introduced to ensure the rights and legal interests of juveniles. It should be noted that there are currently 19 juvenile courts operating in Kazakhstan.

Studies show that the juvenile justice system is developed in many foreign countries, and this institution has a positive effect in protecting the rights of juveniles, preventing delinquency among them, and bringing them to justice for their crimes. Currently, the Juvenile Justice system is widely developed in more than 60 foreign countries.

Based on the experience of developed foreign countries, it is appropriate to implement measures to introduce the juvenile justice system in our country.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the use of the best practices of developed foreign countries in protecting the rights and legitimate interests of juveniles, their social support, as well as in exercising prosecutorial supervision in this area, improving our national legislation and thereby increasing the effectiveness of prosecutorial and control activities of the prosecutor's office is important.

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